

1 **Title**

2 **COMPASS: A Web-Based COMposite Activity Scoring System to**
3 **Navigate Health and Disease Through Deterministic Digital Biomarkers**

4 **Authors**

5 Saptarshi Sinha^{1,3*} and Pradipta Ghosh^{1-3*}

6 Departments of ¹Cellular and Molecular Medicine and ²Medicine, and ³Institute for Network Medicine,
7 University of California, San Diego, CA, 92093, USA.

8 *Correspondence to sasinha@health.ucsd.edu (SS) or prghosh@ucsd.edu (P.G).

9 **Keywords**

10 Gene expression analysis · Data-driven thresholding · Composite activity scoring · Pathway
11 quantification · Precision medicine · Cohort anchoring · New Approach Methods (NAMs) · Outcome
12 simulation

13

Abstract (195 words)

Quantifying pathway activity in a reproducible and interpretable manner remains a central challenge in systems biology and precision medicine. Here, we introduce COMPASS (COMposite Activity Scoring System), a deterministic, ontology-free, threshold-based framework that converts gene expression into per-sample pathway activity scores without reliance on permutation or reference cohorts. Implemented as an intuitive web application, COMPASS derives gene-specific activation thresholds directly from data, standardizes deviations from these boundaries, and integrates directionally opposing genes into a single composite score using closed-form logic. Implemented as an accessible web application, COMPASS enables users to upload expression matrices, define gene signatures, and perform activity scoring, statistical comparisons, and survival analyses without coding. Across diverse biological and clinical datasets, COMPASS generates stable and transferable digital biomarkers that quantify cellular states, benchmark 'humanness' and 'relevance' of model systems and enable outcome stratification. In head-to-head comparisons with widely used single-sample enrichment methods (GSVA and ssGSEA), COMPASS shows consistent performance across multi-cohort datasets, with improved discrimination when integrating bidirectional gene programs. Stratified bootstrap analyses further demonstrate reduced variability and increased robustness. By directly linking expression thresholds, deviation, and gene directionality, COMPASS provides a transparent and generalizable framework for ontology-free pathway activity quantification and outcome modeling.

Impact statement

COMPASS redefines pathway analysis by replacing permutation-based enrichment with a closed-form, threshold-driven framework that yields robust, interpretable, and clinically actionable activity scores, enabling reproducible, sample-level pathway scoring without coding and bridging gene expression to clinically meaningful outcomes.

38 Introduction

39 Understanding how genes act collectively to define cellular states remains a central challenge in systems biology.
40 Widely used enrichment-based methods (e.g., GSEA¹, GSVA², ssGSEA³, PLAGE⁴, AUCell⁵, and VAM⁶) quantify
41 *relative* enrichment rather than *absolute* activity, relying on evolving ontologies and permutation statistics (**Fig.**
42 **1a-left**). These dependencies introduce variability across datasets, platforms, and time, limiting reproducibility
43 and complicating interpretation in translational settings⁷⁻⁹. In addition, many clinically relevant gene signatures
44 contain both upregulated and downregulated genes; when treated as undirected gene sets, opposing biological
45 signals may be conflated, leading to inconsistent interpretation.

46 Here, we introduce **COMPASS (COMPOSITE Activity Scoring System)**, a deterministic, ontology-free,
47 and web-based framework that quantifies gene-set activity directly from expression data (**Fig. 1a-middle**).
48 COMPASS derives gene-specific activation thresholds, standardizes deviations from these boundaries, and
49 integrates oppositely regulated genes into a single composite score using closed-form logic. This approach
50 transforms gene expression into stable, interpretable, and transferable digital biomarkers at the sample level.

51

52 Results and Discussion

53 A deterministic, threshold-based framework for pathway activity quantification

54 COMPASS operationalizes a threshold-based view of biological systems, in which cellular states emerge from
55 transitions (high vs low) across expression boundaries [expanded here¹⁰]. Modeled for long using the *Boolean*
56 *Network Explorer* (BoNE¹¹) and formalized recently as **AXIOM-Bio**¹⁰ (*Abstract eXpression Inference*
57 *and Ontology-free Modeling for Biological Logic and Disease*), this framework for creating foundational models
58 of disease continuum states has demonstrated reproducibility across species and diseases^{10,12}. However,
59 BoNE's computational complexity has limited accessibility. By embedding this logic in an accessible and intuitive
60 web platform (<https://compass.precsn.com/>), COMPASS enables users to interpret raw expression data using
61 gene sets as deterministic digital biomarkers with minimal technical overhead, bridging biological reasoning,
62 computational rigor, and translational relevance (**Fig. 1a-right**).

63 Unlike enrichment-based methods (GSEA¹, GSVA², ssGSEA³, PLAGE⁴, AUCell⁵, and VAM⁶) that depend
64 on ranked gene lists and random permutations, COMPASS deterministically measures biological activity without
65 reference to predefined ontologies. In contrast to matrix-factorization or deep-learning models such as PCA, ICA,
66 NMF, MOFA⁺, or variational autoencoders^{13,14}), COMPASS avoids latent dimensions, retaining interpretability
67 while eliminating stochastic variation.

68 Beyond classification and pathway quantification, translational applications require linking molecular
69 measurements to clinical outcomes. Because COMPASS generates continuous, direction-aware composite
70 scores of any gene set at the sample level, these scores can be directly used to stratify samples into high and

low groups for survival analyses, including Kaplan–Meier analysis and Cox proportional hazards modeling. This enables a single digital biomarker to support classification, cross-cohort benchmarking, and outcome prediction within a unified deterministic framework. Importantly, because thresholds are derived directly from the data rather than from evolving ontologies, COMPASS outputs are reproducible over time for a given dataset and gene signature, and are transferable across platforms, tissues, cohorts, and species.

Mathematical formulation of COMPASS: thresholding, standardization, and aggregation

The COMPASS workflow transforms a raw gene-expression matrix into deterministic, quantitative measures of pathway activity through a three-step process: (i) thresholding, (ii) standardization, and (iii) aggregation (Fig. 1b; see *Methods*). Each step corresponds to a concrete, interpretable biological operation rather than an abstract statistical transformation.

Briefly, in the thresholding step, COMPASS identifies for every gene its intrinsic expression boundary based on the given sample set and its inflection point where its expression pattern transitions dramatically from “off” to “on”. This data-driven threshold, determined automatically by adaptive segmentation algorithms, pinpoints where biological probability collapses into commitment. The standardization step aligns genes of varying dynamic range onto a unified scale, transforming noisy expression profiles into interpretable distance measures that indicate how far each gene lies from its activation point. Finally, the aggregation step integrates these standardized deviations across genes within a defined set, applying direction-specific weights to capture the balance of opposing influences. The resulting composite score represents the net activation of a pathway in each sample and rank them based on the gene set.

Unlike enrichment-based methods that rely on predefined ontologies or random permutations, COMPASS derives gene-specific thresholds directly from expression data, converts deviations from these thresholds into standardized metrics, and integrates them to compute composite activity scores. All computations are closed form and deterministic: identical input produces identical output, ensuring reproducibility, auditability, and mathematical transparency. The three steps are further expanded below:

1. Threshold determination (biological decision boundaries): At the core of COMPASS lies the *StepMiner*¹⁵ algorithm, an adaptive algorithm originally developed to identify sharp transcriptional transitions from noisy expression data. For each gene g , the expression values across samples are sorted, and a step function is fit to this ordered distribution. The transition index (T_g) represents the inflection point that minimizes within-group variance—corresponding to the biological boundary between low (“off”) and high (“on”) expression states.

For each gene g and sample i , COMPASS computes a normalized deviation from the threshold as:

$$E_{g,i} = \begin{cases} \mu_{g,0}, & i < T_g \\ \mu_{g,1}, & i \geq T_g \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Where T_g denotes the transition index minimizing within-group variance. This threshold defines the binary states “low (0)” and “high (1)” expression. This adaptive segmentation identifies the intrinsic activation threshold for each gene directly from data, without requiring any external annotation or training. Conceptually, this threshold identifies where biological probability collapses into commitment (“off” → “on”)¹⁰. In doing so, thresholding reveals the cellular decision boundary.

To minimize stochastic fluctuations around this boundary, COMPASS applies a small confidence offset (σ) to the threshold, defining the final decision boundary of each gene g as:

$$T^*_g = T_g + \sigma \quad (2)$$

where, $\sigma = 0.5 \log_2 \text{Units}$. This conservative shift in threshold ensures that only values confidently above or below the step contribute to the score.

2. Standardization (normalization across genes): Once thresholds are established, each gene’s deviation from its intrinsic boundary is standardized relative to its variance, yielding a dimensionless measure of distance from the decision point: For every gene g and sample i , the deviation from this intrinsic threshold is standardized as:

$$Z_{g,i} = \frac{E_{g,i} - T_g}{\sigma_g} \quad (3)$$

where $E_{g,i}$ is the observed expression and σ_g the gene-specific standard deviation. $Z_{g,i}$ thus measures the distance from the decision boundary¹¹, producing a hybrid metric: discrete when categorical precision is needed (i.e., digital) and continuous when population gradients matter (i.e., analog). The standardized deviation used in COMPASS is then calculated as:

$$Z_{g,i} = \frac{E_{g,i} - T^*_g}{3\sigma_g} \quad (4)$$

Dividing by $3\sigma_g$ (instead of $1 \times \sigma_g$) compresses extreme outliers and brings all genes to a comparable dynamic scale. This preserves biological directionality while reducing threshold-adjacent noise.

This standardization step converts heterogeneous expression profiles into a common coordinate system in which each $Z_{g,i}$ representing how strongly a gene deviates from its activation threshold.

3. Composite aggregation (pathway-level integration): For any gene-set, $G = \{g_1, g_2, \dots, g_m\}$, COMPASS computes the composite activity score for each sample i as the weighted mean of standardized deviations:

$$C_i = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{j=1}^m w_j Z_{g_j,i} \quad (5)$$

where weights w_j encode gene directionality (+1 = activation, -1 = repression). The resulting composite score (C_i) reflects the net balance of activation and repression, providing an interpretable, quantitative index of pathway

131 activity. A higher positive value indicates dominance of activation, while a negative value indicates repression.
132 Published use cases include pro- versus anti-inflammatory macrophage states¹⁶, differentiation versus
133 stemness¹⁷, or metabolic activation versus inhibition, within a single continuous framework.

134 This closed-form calculation eliminates the randomness inherent to permutation-based enrichment
135 methods. It also ensures that each component—expression, threshold, deviation, and directionality—
136 corresponds to an observable biological quantity rather than a statistical abstraction.

137 To evaluate biological and clinical relevance, COMPASS rank the sample set based on the derived
138 composite scores and perform a ROC–AUC analysis, comparing the classification accuracy of defined sample
139 groups (for example, disease vs control or responder vs non-responder) based on another *Stepminer* threshold
140 computed on the composite scores. The Area Under the Curve (AUC) is computed as:

$$141 \quad AUC = P(C_i^A > C_j^B) \quad (6)$$

142 where C_i^A and C_j^B denote the composite scores of state *A* (e.g., treated or disease) and state *B* (e.g., control or
143 healthy) samples, respectively. This provides a universal, model-agnostic measure of discriminatory power that
144 reflects the internal biological coherence of each gene-set's activity pattern and serves as a statistical summary
145 the same. Because all operations are deterministic, identical inputs produce identical outputs, ensuring
146 reproducibility and traceability across runs, datasets, and environments.

147

148 **A web-based platform for reproducible, code-free pathway activity scoring**

149 COMPASS is implemented as a web-based analytical platform (<https://compass.precsn.com/>) with an
150 intuitive graphical interface (**Fig. 1c; Figure Supplement S1**). Users upload a tab- or comma-delimited gene
151 expression matrix (txt, tsv, or csv), optionally include time-to-event metadata, define gene signatures with
152 directionality, and initiate analysis through a point-and-click workflow. All computations, including thresholding,
153 standardization, aggregation, and statistical evaluation, are executed automatically in the background, without
154 the need for pathway databases or coding. Gene-set definitions are fully customizable, with flexibility to assign
155 directionality weights (+/-).

156 The platform generates publication-ready outputs, including boxplots for group comparisons
157 (accompanied by pairwise *t*-test statistics), ROC–AUC analyses (with associated *F* and *p* values), composite
158 activity tables (containing standardized Z-scores and composite scores for each pathway and sample), and
159 survival analyses (with hazard ratios and log-rank statistics). Results are downloadable in standard formats
160 (CSV, PDF).

161 In terms of accessibility, unlike conventional computational frameworks, COMPASS is designed to be
162 intuitive and accessible to both computational and non-computational users. Users can define and compare any

number of sample groups directly from their uploaded data (e.g., WT vs KO, responders vs non-responders, multiple treatment conditions). The interface enables point-and-click selection of genes, pathways, and groups, generating publication-ready figures without manual scripting (Fig. S1a-b). All statistical analyses, such as composite score calculation, group-wise comparisons, ROC–AUC, survival analyses are performed automatically. By integrating accessibility with mathematical transparency, COMPASS enables consistent, sample-level quantification of pathway activity across biological and clinical contexts.

Clinically anchored benchmarking across multi-cohort datasets

COMPASS supports diverse use cases (see Fig. 1d-f): benchmarking organoids, animal models, or New Approach Methodologies (NAMs) against human cohorts to quantify *humanness* and biological *relevance*¹⁷⁻²³; computing composite activity scores predictive of outcomes¹⁷; tracking drug response or toxicity²¹; and mapping disease-driver cell states such as alveolar cytopathy, immune cell processes (reactivity vs. tolerance) or differentiation^{11,16,17,24}.

Across diverse gene signatures and datasets spanning oncology, infectious disease, inflammatory disorders, and cellular state mapping (Fig. 2a-o), COMPASS consistently recapitulated expected biological patterns across human cohorts, animal models, and organoid systems. In colorectal cancer, a stemness signature quantified concordant therapeutic responses across cell lines, xenografts, and patient-derived organoids. In colorectal cancer, a 50-gene stemness signature¹⁷ quantified the efficacy of a differentiation-inducing therapeutic across cell lines, xenografts, and patient-derived organoids, revealing concordant pathway suppression in all models (Fig. 2a-c). In respiratory viral injury²⁵, COMPASS detected induction of a lung damage signature across infected human biopsies, hamster lungs, and adult stem cell-derived lung organoids (Fig. 2d-f), highlighting conserved molecular pathology.

Clinical (diagnostic and prognostic) signatures for sepsis²⁶, breast cancer²⁷, and idiopathic pulmonary fibrosis²⁸ generated robust discriminatory scores aligned with clinical classifications (Fig. 2g-i). In two independent IBD clinical trials, a bioenergetic barrier signature²¹ stratified responders from non-responders across therapeutic classes and tracked remission longitudinally (Fig. 2j-m). Finally, COMPASS quantified cell-state transitions—capturing induction of DATPs in fibrosis models²⁹ and defining graded polarization from macrophage reactivity to tolerance¹⁶ (Fig. 2n-o).

These results demonstrate consistent performance across cohorts, models, and species, supporting the use of COMPASS for cross-context benchmarking and outcome-linked digital biomarker modeling.

Benchmarking against other methodologies: Reduced variability and enhanced robustness under resampling.

196 **Table 1** highlights key differences between COMPASS and other enrichment-based gene set scoring
197 methods. Unlike other approaches, which compute relative, cohort-dependent scores, COMPASS derives gene-
198 specific thresholds and generates absolute, direction-aware activity scores at the sample level. This deterministic
199 formulation avoids permutations, improves reproducibility, and enables stable integration of opposing gene
200 signals. In addition, COMPASS supports multi-class and continuous analyses, facilitating consistent pathway
201 quantification across datasets and biological contexts.

202 To position COMPASS relative to widely used single-sample scoring methods, we performed head-to-
203 head comparisons against GSEA and ssGSEA across 10 independent cohorts (comprised of 232 control and
204 499 sepsis samples) spanning diverse clinical contexts and patient populations using a clinically validated 11-
205 gene sepsis signature²⁶. This signature was originally identified and rigorously validated in multi-cohort
206 datasets^{26,30} (**Fig. 3a**), and recently approved by the FDA for marketing. To assess the role of gene directionality,
207 analyses were conducted using upregulated genes, downregulated genes, and the full composite signature.

208 Across cohorts, GSEA and ssGSEA showed variable performance depending on gene subset and cohort
209 composition, particularly when directional (upregulated or downregulated) components were evaluated
210 separately (for example, **Fig. 3b-c**; **Figure Supplement S2a-b**). By contrast, COMPASS maintained consistent
211 discrimination when integrating directionally opposing genes into a single composite score (for example, **Fig. 3d**;
212 **Figure Supplement S2c**), highlighting the importance of direction-aware aggregation for stable pathway
213 quantification.

214 Robustness was evaluated using stratified bootstrap resampling (n = 1000; **Fig. 4a**). For each bootstrap
215 replicate, AUC was recalculated, with score direction aligned when necessary to ensure consistent interpretation.
216 Sensitivity and specificity were estimated using a fixed decision threshold for each method, determined once
217 from the original dataset by maximizing the Youden index and then applied uniformly across all bootstrap
218 replicates. COMPASS exhibited tighter AUC distributions and higher central tendency across cohorts (**Fig. 4b-**
219 **k**), indicating reduced variance and stability under sampling perturbation. GSEA and ssGSEA showed broader
220 distributions, reflecting greater sensitivity to cohort composition/resampling. Quantitative summaries (**Table 2**)
221 further support these findings. COMPASS achieved balanced performance across cohorts, (mean specificity of
222 0.92 and sensitivity of 0.91). Notably, these values approach the performance range reported for the SEPSIS-
223 SHIELD clinical study³⁰ (specificity >92% and sensitivity >95%), indicating that COMPASS-derived scores
224 recapitulate clinically relevant discriminatory power at the cohort level. By contrast, GSEA (specificity 0.69,
225 sensitivity 0.69) and ssGSEA (specificity 0.80, sensitivity 0.88) showed substantially lower and less balanced
226 performance.

227 Together, these analyses demonstrate that direction-aware, deterministic scoring improves stability and
228 reproducibility of pathway activity quantification across cohorts.

Outcome prediction and survival stratification using COMPASS-derived scores

To assess clinical relevance, we analyzed a large multi-cohort sepsis dataset (**GSE310929**; n = 593 patients) with time to death annotation using a validated 12-gene sepsis-severity signature^{30,31} (**Fig. 5a-b**). As in the case of the 11-gene diagnostic signature we used earlier (**Fig. 3a**), this 12-gene severity signature was also rigorously validated in the SEPSIS-SHIELD clinical study³⁰ before receiving regulatory approval for marketing. Enrichment-based methods, as well as COMPASS showed comparable performance in sample classification (**Fig. 5c-e**); all underperformed to similar extent. Importantly, COMPASS-derived scores enabled direct stratification of patients by survival outcome (**Fig. 5f**). Patients with higher composite scores exhibited significantly worse survival (Hazard ratio [H.R] = 2.32), demonstrating that deterministic, direction-aware activity scores can be extended from group discrimination to time-to-event analysis.

These results establish that COMPASS provides a unified framework in which pathway activity scores function as outcome-linked digital biomarkers, enabling consistent transition from classification to survival modeling within the same analytical system.

Conclusions

The benchmarking analyses presented here position COMPASS alongside existing single-sample scoring methods rather than replacing them. Approaches such as GSVA and ssGSEA remain valuable for relative enrichment analysis. By contrast, by explicitly modeling gene directionality and anchoring expression to intrinsic thresholds, COMPASS provides a complementary, deterministic framework that improves interpretability and stability. Beyond that, a conceptual advance that is operationalized through COMPASS is its ability to integrate opposing biological signals within composite signatures. Bootstrap analyses (**Table 2**) further support reduced variability and consistent performance across cohorts, and demonstrable superiority in the setting of opposing biological signals across diverse cohorts.

Another key advance of COMPASS is its ability to directly link pathway activity to clinical outcomes. By generating continuous, direction-aware composite scores at the sample level, COMPASS enables seamless integration with survival frameworks, allowing the same digital biomarker to support classification, cross-cohort benchmarking, and time-to-event modeling. This unification bridges molecular measurement with clinically meaningful endpoints without reliance on stochastic inference or intermediate model fitting.

More broadly, COMPASS establishes a generalizable framework for pathway activity quantification and outcome modeling. Its deterministic design ensures that identical inputs yield identical outputs, enabling reproducibility across datasets, platforms, and settings, including regulatory contexts. By linking expression, threshold, deviation, and directionality within a transparent, closed-form system, COMPASS converts gene-

262 expression data into interpretable and transferable measures of biological state, providing a foundation for
263 consistent and scalable analysis across model systems and clinical cohorts.

264
265 **Limitations:**

266 This study has several limitations. Because COMPASS derives thresholds directly from input data, its
267 performance depends on data quality and preprocessing (e.g., normalization) and may be affected by limited
268 dynamic range or residual batch effects. The framework assumes that gene expression can be partitioned around
269 meaningful activation thresholds; genes with weak or unimodal expression patterns may therefore contribute
270 less information. In addition, COMPASS relies on biologically informed gene signatures with correctly specified
271 directionality, which requires users to assess the rigor of prior work that led to the discovery of the gene
272 signature(s) and care in accurately assigning gene weight. The current implementation aggregates gene
273 contributions linearly and does not explicitly model higher-order gene–gene interactions or network structure.
274 Benchmarking was performed against widely used enrichment methods, and further evaluation across additional
275 approaches, data modalities (e.g., single-cell, spatial transcriptomics, etc.), and prospective clinical settings will
276 be important to establish generalizability. Finally, while COMPASS-derived scores can be integrated with survival
277 analyses, these associations do not constitute fully adjusted predictive models incorporating clinical covariates.

278 **Data Availability:** Example expression matrices and gene-signature files used to generate Figure 2 and related
279 analyses are available at our GitHub repository: <https://github.com/sinha7290/COMPASS>. The COMPASS web
280 application implementing the composite activity scoring framework is freely accessible at
281 <https://compass.precsn.com/>. Further information and requests for resources should be directed to and will be
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289 developed the web tool. P.G. provided key resources. S.S. and P.G. jointly selected datasets and gene
290 signatures, prepared figures, wrote, reviewed, and edited the manuscript. Both authors approved the final version
291 of the manuscript.

292 **Declaration of interests:** Authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Materials and methods

Gene expression datasets and preprocessing: Previously published bulk gene-expression datasets used for benchmarking COMPASS are described in the main text. For each study, normalized expression matrices were obtained from the original publication, GEO/ArrayExpress, or were reprocessed from raw counts using standard RNA-seq pipelines (alignment, quantification, and normalization). When raw data were available, counts were converted to transcripts per million (TPM) or counts-per-million (CPM) with \log_2 transformation. When only processed data were available (e.g., \log_2 intensity values from microarrays), those matrices were used directly after confirming that sample-wise distributions were unimodal and approximately comparable across groups. Genes with zero or near-zero variance across samples were excluded because they do not contribute meaningfully to composite scores. All COMPASS analyses were performed on gene-by-sample matrices in which rows correspond to genes and columns correspond to samples, with samples annotated by user-defined biological or clinical group labels.

Gene signatures: For all analyses in this study, gene lists and direction assignments were curated from prior experimental work, literature-derived pathways, or Boolean implication networks, as detailed in the main text.

COMPASS composite activity scoring: Composite activity scores were calculated using COMPASS as defined in Equations (1–5) in the main text. Briefly, \log_2 -normalized gene expression matrices (e.g., TPM or counts-per-million) were used as input. For each gene, COMPASS estimated a data-driven activation threshold by fitting a step function to the ordered expression values and identifying the position that minimized the within-group variance, thereby classifying samples as “low” or “high” expressors. Expression deviations from this threshold were then standardized by the across-sample standard deviation to generate direction-aware z-scores. For each predefined gene set or signature, per-sample composite activity scores were obtained as the weighted average of these z-scores, with +1 weights assigned to genes expected to increase and –1 weights to genes expected to decrease with pathway activation. The resulting scores are deterministic (no permutations) and were used to generate boxplots, group-wise comparisons, and receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curves for user-specified biological or clinical contrasts. All analyses were performed using the COMPASS web application (<https://compass.precsn.com>).

Survival analysis and outcome modeling: Survival analysis was performed using COMPASS-derived scores as continuous predictors. Patients’ metadata with time to event annotation were used as input. Patients were stratified into high and low groups using a *StepMiner*-derived cutoff applied to the distribution of composite scores within each cohort. Kaplan–Meier curves were used to estimate time-to-event (30-day mortality) probabilities, with significance assessed by log-rank test. Hazard ratios (HRs) and corresponding confidence intervals were estimated using Cox proportional hazards models, treating COMPASS scores as either continuous or dichotomized variables. In datasets where samples are annotated for the presence or absence of

an event/outcome, as well as time to such outcome/event, the same composite metric used for classification and ROC analysis can be directly applied to survival modeling without additional transformation or retraining.

Quantification and Statistical Analysis: For each gene module or signature, COMPASS computed a single continuous composite activity score per sample as described in the main text. These scores served as the primary quantitative readout for all downstream analyses. For group-wise comparisons, samples were assigned to user-defined biological or clinical groups, and composite scores were compared using two-sided Welch's t-tests (unequal variances). Raw p-values were assembled into a group \times group matrix and adjusted for multiple testing using both Bonferroni and Benjamini–Hochberg false discovery rate (FDR) procedures; both raw and adjusted values were exported for interpretation. For classification performance, a designated reference group was treated as the negative class and each other group as the positive class. Receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curves and corresponding areas under the curve (AUCs) were computed from composite scores using standard empirical estimators, and AUC p-values were obtained from asymptotic normal approximations. All tests were two-sided and based on complete-case data. For survival analysis log rank test, hazard ratio was also calculated. Analyses were implemented in Python within the COMPASS web application using standard scientific libraries (numpy, pandas, scipy, scikit-learn), with visualization modules generating boxplots, ROC curves, KM plot for export.

Head-to-head comparison with GSVA and ssGSEA: Gene set activity was quantified using two widely used single-sample enrichment methods, Gene Set Variation Analysis (GSVA) and single-sample Gene Set Enrichment Analysis (ssGSEA), implemented via the GSEAPy package (v1.1.13) with default parameters unless otherwise specified (including kernel type, normalization, and gene set size thresholds). GSVA estimates pathway activity by modeling the distribution of gene expression values across samples using a non-parametric kernel transformation, whereas ssGSEA computes a rank-based enrichment score independently within each sample. In parallel, a deterministic composite score was computed using the COMPASS framework. In this approach, gene expression values were transformed into standardized deviations from *StepMiner*-derived thresholds with noise margin (T^*), scaled by gene-specific variance to generate dimensionless Z-scores. These normalized values were then aggregated using predefined gene-specific weights to generate a directionality-aware composite activity score at the sample level. Directionality weights (+1 for activation, -1 for repression) were assigned based on prior biological annotation of each gene and held constant across all analyses.

Method performance was evaluated by assessing the ability of GSVA, ssGSEA, and COMPASS scores to discriminate sepsis from healthy controls using ROC analysis and the corresponding AUC. Score orientation was aligned across methods such that higher values consistently corresponded to the disease (sepsis) state prior to ROC analysis. To assess robustness, stratified bootstrap resampling ($n = 1000$) was performed with replacement within each class using a fixed random seed to ensure reproducibility. AUC was computed for each bootstrap replicate, and the resulting distributions were used to estimate mean performance and 95% confidence intervals based on percentile statistics. Sensitivity and specificity were computed using a fixed decision threshold

362 for each method, determined on the full, original cohort by maximizing the Youden index³² and applied
363 consistently across bootstrap replicates.

364 Traditional GSEA was not applied because it produces cohort-level enrichment statistics rather than
365 sample-level scores.

366

Tables and Figures

Table 1 | Comparative features of COMPASS versus existing gene-set activity frameworks. Acronyms: GSEA, Gene Set Enrichment Analysis; GSVA, Gene Set Variation Analysis; ssGSEA, Single-Sample Gene Set Enrichment Analysis; PLAGE, Pathway-Level Analysis of Gene Expression; AUCcell, Area-Under-the-Curve Cell Scoring; VAM, Variance-Adjusted Mahalanobis.

Feature	COMPASS	GSEA	GSVA	ssGSEA	PLAGE	AUCcell / VAM
Full Name	COMPOSITE Activity Scoring System	Gene Set Enrichment Analysis	Gene Set Variation Analysis for microarray & RNA-Seq	Single-Sample Gene Set Enrichment Analysis	Pathway Level Analysis of Gene Expression	AUC-based Cell Scoring & Variance-Adjusted Mahalanobis
Key Feature	Deterministic, ontology-free, web-based digital biomarker quantification	Permutation-based enrichment; ontology-dependent	Unsupervised variation of gene-set enrichment across samples	Per-sample enrichment scoring; extension of GSEA	Singular value decomposition (SVD)-based modeling of pathway activity	Single-cell activity scoring via AUC and variance-adjusted methods
Lead Institution	Institute for Network Medicine, UC San Diego, USA	Broad Institute, MIT-Harvard	Universitat Pompeu Fabra & Sage Bionetworks	Broad Institute, MIT-Harvard	Columbia University & KRIBB (Korea)	Center for Genomic Regulation (Spain) / University of Alabama
Publication (Year)	Sinha & Ghosh, 2025 (This Study)	Subramanian et al., PNAS 2005 ¹	Hänzelmann et al., BMC Bioinformatics 2013 ²	Barbie et al., Nature 2009 ³	Kim & Volsky, BMC Bioinformatics 2005 ⁴	Aibar et al., Nature Methods 2017 ⁵ ; Frost et al., Bioinformatics 2021 ⁶
Data-derived thresholding	Yes (adaptive per gene)	No	No	No	No	No
Deterministic output (run-to-run identical)	Yes	No (permutation-based)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Coding required to run	No (web app)	No (web app / desktop client)	Yes (R)	Yes (R)	Yes (R)	Yes (R / Python)
Assigned gene weights (+ / - per gene)	Yes (activation vs repression encoded)	No	No	No	No	No
Absolute per-sample activity score (digital biomarker)	Yes (composite activity index)	No (relative enrichment only)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Ontology-independent (custom gene sets allowed)	Yes (fully user-defined)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Single-sample scoring	Yes	No (requires two-class contrast)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Handles >2 groups / graded trajectories	Yes (multi-class and continua)	No (two-group only)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Robust with very small n (<5 samples / group)	Yes	No (needs group sizes for permutations)	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate	Yes
Noise handling via intrinsic, data-driven thresholds	Yes (per-gene decision boundary)	No	No	No	No	No
Speed	Very fast (closed form; no permutations)	Slow (permutation testing)	Fast	Fast	Fast	Fast
Interpretability (reasoning and explainability)	High (Grounded in Foundational Model of Biological Logic ¹⁰)	Moderate, knowledge based (enrichment probability)	Moderate, knowledge based	Moderate, knowledge based	Moderate, knowledge based	Moderate, knowledge based
Transparency of computation	High (no latent dimensions / no sampling)	Low (randomization, ranked lists)	Medium	Medium	Medium	Medium
Cross-dataset reproducibility	High (deterministic, platform-agnostic)	Low-Medium	Medium	Medium	Medium	Medium
Availability / licensing	Open source	Open source	Open source (R package)	Open source (R package)	Open source (R package)	Open source
Web-based interface	Yes (no coding required)	Yes (Broad GSEA Web / desktop app)	No	No	No	Partial (via SCENIC / portals)
Integrated survival analysis / HR estimation	Yes	No	No	No	No	No

Table 2. Stratified bootstrap performance of GSVa, ssGSEA, and COMPASS across independent cohorts: Performance metrics are summarized from bootstrap resampling (n = 1000) performed independently within each class (cases and controls) to preserve class balance. For each iteration, receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curves were used to derive area under the curve (AUC) values, from which mean AUC and 95% confidence intervals (CI) were estimated. Sensitivity and specificity were calculated using a fixed decision threshold for each method, determined from the original dataset by maximizing the Youden index and applied consistently across iterations. Sensitivity and specificity are presented as mean \pm standard deviation (S.D) in each cohort (left), and as averages across bootstrap iterations (right).

Dataset	Method	Mean AUC	95% CI (AUC)	Sensitivity (mean \pm SD)	Specificity (mean \pm SD)
GSE40012	GSVA	0.760	(0.683-0.828)	0.624 \pm 0.038	0.861 \pm 0.058
	ssGSEA	0.749	(0.683-0.812)	0.631 \pm 0.037	0.946 \pm 0.038
	COMPASS	0.960	(0.935-0.983)	0.910 \pm 0.023	0.917 \pm 0.048
GSE32707	GSVA	0.670	(0.563-0.773)	0.935 \pm 0.024	0.376 \pm 0.084
	ssGSEA	0.619	(0.497-0.735)	0.982 \pm 0.012	0.376 \pm 0.084
	COMPASS	0.854	(0.780-0.921)	0.864 \pm 0.033	0.736 \pm 0.077
GSE11755	GSVA	0.571	(0.377-0.755)	0.743 \pm 0.079	0.494 \pm 0.158
	ssGSEA	0.589	(0.390-0.784)	0.292 \pm 0.079	1.000 \pm 0.000
	COMPASS	0.955	(0.865-1.000)	1.000 \pm 0.000	0.801 \pm 0.126
GSE13015	GSVA	0.757	(0.612-0.882)	0.836 \pm 0.053	0.685 \pm 0.109
	ssGSEA	0.945	(0.888-0.986)	0.918 \pm 0.040	0.843 \pm 0.085
	COMPASS	0.990	(0.969-1.000)	0.980 \pm 0.020	0.947 \pm 0.052
GSE27131	GSVA	0.753	(0.520-0.939)	0.789 \pm 0.107	0.712 \pm 0.172
	ssGSEA	0.871	(0.704-1.000)	0.790 \pm 0.106	1.000 \pm 0.000
	COMPASS	1.000	(1.000-1.000)	1.000 \pm 0.000	1.000 \pm 0.000
GSE40396	GSVA	0.731	(0.600-0.851)	0.605 \pm 0.078	0.820 \pm 0.081
	ssGSEA	0.795	(0.675-0.903)	0.696 \pm 0.070	0.908 \pm 0.062
	COMPASS	0.847	(0.749-0.936)	0.698 \pm 0.071	0.864 \pm 0.071
GSE25504	GSVA	0.599	(0.446-0.737)	0.423 \pm 0.097	0.787 \pm 0.068
	ssGSEA	0.889	(0.788-0.967)	0.884 \pm 0.062	0.837 \pm 0.062
	COMPASS	0.924	(0.850-0.976)	0.885 \pm 0.062	0.835 \pm 0.060
GSE28750	GSVA	0.556	(0.345-0.780)	0.896 \pm 0.096	0.548 \pm 0.112
	ssGSEA	0.970	(0.895-1.000)	0.901 \pm 0.096	0.949 \pm 0.049
	COMPASS	1.000	(1.000-1.000)	1.000 \pm 0.000	1.000 \pm 0.000
GSE33341	GSVA	0.592	(0.507-0.695)	0.575 \pm 0.248	0.653 \pm 0.245
	ssGSEA	0.980	(0.953-0.997)	0.946 \pm 0.033	0.967 \pm 0.030
	COMPASS	1.000	(1.000-1.000)	1.000 \pm 0.000	1.000 \pm 0.000
GSE21802	GSVA	0.742	(0.458-0.958)	0.497 \pm 0.141	1.000 \pm 0.000
	ssGSEA	0.956	(0.833-1.000)	0.914 \pm 0.081	1.000 \pm 0.000
	COMPASS	0.979	(0.875-1.000)	0.916 \pm 0.082	1.000 \pm 0.000

Figure 1. Overview of the COMPASS Framework for translational Integration of Digital Biomarkers Across Models and Cohorts Using COMPASS.

The conceptual foundation (a), computational workflow (b), and workflow for translational integration of digital biomarkers for analyzing gene expression data to derive logic-based pathway activation scores and digital biomarkers.

(a) Conceptual Foundation: COMPASS addresses limitations of traditional logic modeling by offering a deterministic, reproducible, and accessible framework for translational precision medicine.

(b) Computational Workflow: Workflow schematic showing user inputs (expression matrix, gene signature, logic), automated backend computations, and outputs including box plots, ROC-AUC analyses and survival analyses.

(c) User Interface: Example of an intuitive interface and downloadable outputs demonstrating COMPASS's ability to stratify groups and assess pathway activation with statistical significance, while remaining accessible to all biologists.

(d-f) Translational Workflow: Workflow schematic illustrates a three-part framework for aligning diverse biological models with cohort-level measurements through digital biomarkers and the COMPASS system. **(d) Cohort-Level Discovery:** Disease driver events, clinical endpoints, and regulatory endpoints are identified from large-n human trial datasets. These serve as anchors for downstream modeling and validation. **(e) Model-Level Quantification:** Diverse experimental platforms—including cell lines, patient-derived organoids (PDOs), ex vivo tissues (e.g., precision-cut tissue slices, live or fixed), organs-on-chip, and animal models—are evaluated using digital biomarkers. COMPASS objectively quantifies the humanness and relevance of each model's response, enabling cross-comparison and translational alignment. **(f) Cohort-Level Benchmarking and Simulation:** Validated digital biomarkers are used to simulate cohort-level responses with high objectivity and precision. In silico trials (with survival analysis) further extend predictive capacity, supporting regulatory decision-making and personalized medicine. Central to this framework, COMPASS acts as a translational bridge linking small-n mechanistic studies with large-n population insights and enabling iterative refinement of digital biomarkers across biological scales.

Figure Supplement S1 [related to Figure 1]. Computational Workflow and User Interface of COMPASS.

(a) **Workflow schematic.** From a user-supplied gene expression matrix (txt/tsv/csv), a sample metadata file with time to event annotation (optional), a defined gene signature (with optional weights), and sample group annotations, COMPASS executes a stepwise, transparent pipeline: (i) thresholding using *StepMiner* to define expression cutoffs, (ii) standardization of expression as deviation from threshold, (iii) aggregation of weighted deviations to generate composite pathway activity scores, and (iv) validation by benchmarking against biological or clinical states using ROC-AUC analysis and survival analysis. Outputs include publication-ready, downloadable visualizations and statistics: multi-group box plots with pairwise tests, ROC-AUC metrics with F statistics, and Kaplan–Meier curves with hazard ratio and log rank test.

(b) **User interface.** Representative screenshots illustrate the web-based interface across sequential tabs (highlighted in red): *Data Upload*, *Gene Signature & Groups*, *Box Plot & Statistics*, *ROC–AUC & Statistics*, and *Survival Analysis*. The platform enables a code-free workflow in which all backend computations are executed automatically while maintaining mathematical transparency. Example outputs are shown using clinically relevant gene expression signatures applied to human cohorts. The box plot (center) and ROC–AUC plots (right) demonstrate stratification of patients into risk groups based on PAM50 breast cancer subtypes and gene signatures used in the Breast Cancer Index® (BCI™), a clinically validated genomic assay recognized by major oncology guidelines (National Comprehensive Cancer Network [NCCN] and the American Society of Clinical Oncology [ASCO]) for guiding extended endocrine therapy decisions in HR+ early-stage breast cancer. The survival analysis (bottom right) illustrates Kaplan–Meier–based risk stratification of sepsis mortality using a 12-gene Stanford mortality signature³¹, highlighting the ability of COMPASS-derived scores to associate with clinical outcomes ([GSE310929](#)).

Figure 2. Cohort-level anchoring and cross-model benchmarking using COMPASS.

COMPASS enables deterministic quantification of pathway activity across cohorts, tissues, species, and disease models, allowing unified navigation of biological logic and clinical relevance. Published examples illustrating such cross-species and cross-model ontology-free navigation between human, organoid, and animal systems are shown.

(a–c) Colorectal cancer (CRC): A 50-gene CRC stemness signature¹⁷ was used to score the efficacy of a first-in-class differentiation inducing therapeutic agent across cell lines (a), xenografts (b), and patient-derived organoids (c), demonstrating consistent efficacy across experimental models¹⁷.

(d–f) COVID-19 and lung injury: A 20-gene signature²⁵ indicative of severe alveolar damage in the setting of respiratory viral pandemics is induced in CoV-infected human lungs³³ (d), hamster lungs³⁴ (e), and human adult stem cell-derived lung organoids²³ (f), recapitulating conserved pathway activation across species and model systems (datasets and PMIDs annotated).

(g–i) Diagnostic and prognostic digital biomarkers: Distinct gene sets corresponding to sepsis (g; 11-gene diagnostic gene set, identified using a comprehensive time-course-based multicohort analysis of sepsis²⁶), breast cancer subtypes (h; 7-gene **BCI**[™] signature, the only genomic test that is both prognostic and predictive and is recognized by the NCCN and the ASCO[®] Clinical Practice Guideline to identify patients who might benefit from adjuvant anti-estrogen therapy beyond 5 years), and idiopathic pulmonary fibrosis (I; a 153-gene IPF diagnostic signature²⁸, comprised of 76 up and 77 down genes) generated robust discriminatory activity scores, matching known clinical groupings.

(j–m) Digital biomarkers for therapeutic response prediction and tracking: A 34-gene signature²¹, indicative of mucosal barrier bioenergetic state, predicts therapeutic response in Inflammatory bowel disease (IBD) clinical trial datasets, distinguishing responders (high-34) from non-responders (low-34), regardless of class of drug (j-k) and tracks remission during therapy among responders in longitudinal datasets. Wk, week; UC, Ulcerative colitis; CD, Crohn's disease.

(n–o) Molecular signatures of disease-driving cell states: A 6-gene signature of damage-associated transient progenitors (DATP²⁹) is induced in human IPF and murine models that recapitulate fundamental processes in IPF (i.e., impaired ER stress response³⁴; n). Gene signatures of macrophage¹⁶ reactivity (48 genes) and tolerance (232 genes) accurately captured macrophage polarization continua (reactivity vs tolerance; o) across cytokine-stimulated monocytes, revealing deterministic transitions that define physiologic and pathologic spectra.

Figure 3. Clinically anchored benchmarking of COMPASS across multi-cohort sepsis datasets

(a) Schematic represents the clinical and translational trajectory of the 11-gene host-response signature for sepsis. From left to right: A multi-cohort discovery framework identified a minimal gene set that distinguishes sepsis from sterile inflammation, followed by large-scale validation across independent, multi-center cohorts (including SEPSIS-SHIELD³⁰), demonstrating high diagnostic performance and enabling regulatory advancement to an FDA-authorized molecular diagnostic. This clinically validated gene signature provides a digital gene signature and an opportunity for head-to-head comparison of COMPASS with existing analyses frameworks GSVA and ssGSEA for their ability to accurately and reproducibly classify clinically determined sepsis samples from healthy controls across 11 diverse cohorts.

(b-v) Receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curves comparing GSVA (blue), ssGSEA (orange), and COMPASS (green) across independent transcriptomic cohorts. Panels are arranged by gene set composition (columns) and cohort (rows). Columns represent: left, 6 upregulated genes; middle, 5 downregulated genes; right, full 11-gene signature. Rows correspond to distinct clinical cohorts spanning discovery and validation phases: **(b-d)** [GSE40012](#) (pneumonia patients with or without Systemic Inflammatory Response Syndrome [SIRS]), **(e-g)** [GSE32707](#) (early sepsis, SIRS, and acute respiratory distress syndrome [ARDS] samples), **(h-j)** [GSE11755](#) (pediatric intensive care unit [ICU] cohort), **(k-m)** [GSE13015](#) (pathogen-driven sepsis), **(n-p)** [GSE27131](#) (H1N1 with respiratory failure), **(q-s)** [GSE40396](#) (viral and bacterial infections), **(t-v)** [GSE25504](#) (neonatal sepsis).

Across cohorts, enrichment-based methods (GSVA, ssGSEA) show context-dependent performance, particularly when gene directionality is partitioned (up vs down genes). In contrast, COMPASS demonstrates robust and consistent discrimination, with maximal performance when applied to the full bidirectional signature, highlighting its ability to integrate opposing gene programs into a unified, outcome-relevant score. Additional cohorts are shown in **Figure S2**.

Figure Supplement S2 [Related to Figure 3]. Extended multi-cohort benchmarking of COMPASS

Receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curves comparing GSVA (blue), ssGSEA (orange), and COMPASS (green) across additional independent transcriptomic cohorts. These datasets, unique from those shown in Figure 3, represent the remaining validation cohorts for the 11-gene sepsis diagnostic signature (see **Table 2**). (**a–i**) Panels are organized by gene set composition (columns) and cohort (rows). Columns represent: Left: 6 upregulated genes, Middle: 5 downregulated genes, Right: full 11-gene signature. Rows correspond to independent cohorts: (**a–c**) GSE28750 (20 controls vs 10 sepsis), (**d–f**) GSE33341 (43 controls vs 51 bacterial sepsis; *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, and *Streptococcus pneumoniae*), (**g–i**) GSE21802 (4 controls vs 12 early-stage sepsis with innate immune response). Consistent with Figure 3, performance of GSVA and ssGSEA varies with gene subset and cohort context, whereas COMPASS maintains stable and high discrimination, particularly when integrating the full signature. These results extend the primary analysis and reinforce the cohort-anchored robustness of COMPASS across diverse clinical settings.

Figure 4. Comparative robustness of GSVA, ssGSEA, and COMPASS assessed by stratified bootstrap resampling across independent cohorts

(a) Schematic of the bootstrap workflow (top to bottom). Gene expression matrices are used to compute sample-level scores for GSVa, ssGSEA, and COMPASS. Samples are then resampled with replacement within each class (cases and controls) to preserve class balance. This procedure is repeated for 1000 iterations. In each iteration, score direction is aligned when necessary to ensure consistent interpretation, and receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curves are generated to compute area under the curve (AUC). The resulting AUC distributions are summarized to estimate variability and confidence intervals for each method (see **Table 2**).

(b–k) Violin plots showing distributions of AUC values across 1000 bootstrap iterations for GSVa (blue), ssGSEA (orange), and COMPASS (green) in independent cohorts. Each panel corresponds to a dataset used in **Figure 3** and **Figure S2**. Each violin represents the distribution of resampled AUC values under class-balanced conditions.

Figure 5. Outcome prediction and survival stratification using a clinically validated sepsis severity signature.

(a) Clinical and translational trajectory of the 12-gene sepsis severity signature (Stanford mortality score³¹). A multi-cohort analysis identified³¹ a gene signature associated with sepsis severity and 30-day mortality across community- and hospital-acquired infections. Subsequent validation³⁰ across multi-center studies, including the SEPSIS-SHIELD study³⁰, demonstrated clinical utility and supported regulatory advancement, culminating in FDA authorization of a first-in-class molecular diagnostic test. In the current study, this signature is used for head-to-head comparison and outcome modeling.

(b) Composition of the meta-analysis cohort ([GSE310929](#)). Expression data from 28 bulk RNA-seq datasets were harmonized and batch-corrected, yielding 593 patients with time-to-event annotations. Whole blood samples were collected within 48 hours of admission, with in-hospital mortality as the primary outcome.

(c–e) Receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curves comparing GSVA (blue), ssGSEA (orange), and COMPASS (green) for outcome prediction across different gene set compositions. **(C)** 8 upregulated genes **(D)** 4 downregulated genes **(E)** full 12-gene signature. Each panel shows ROC curves for GSVA (blue), ssGSEA (orange), and COMPASS (green), with corresponding area under the curve (AUC) values.

(f) Kaplan–Meier survival analysis based on COMPASS-derived scores using the full 12-gene signature. Patients stratified into high versus low score groups show significantly different survival probabilities, with worse outcomes in the high-score group (hazard ratio [HR] = 2.32, 95% CI: 1.67–3.22; Cox and log rank p-value and log-rank p-values as indicated). Shaded regions represent confidence intervals, and numbers at risk are shown below the plot.

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